

RONNIE GOVENDER AND ASIAN BELONGING WITHIN SOUTH AFRICA

Maurice O'Connor
Universidad de Cádiz
maurice.oconnor@uca.es
ORCID: orcid.org/0000-0002-9984-0581

Abstract

This paper explores the Asian presence in South Africa through the work of Ronnie Govender. One of its concerns is how fictional worlds based on real-life experiences become a means to counter the discourses of apartheid that insisted upon the incommensurability of cultural difference as regards Asian and African communities. In this light, the paper references how a white hegemony sets about compromising an already fragile co-existence that existed between the Black, Coloured, and Asian communities and considers the body of Govender's work as a repository which aids future generations to connect with the traumatic nature of apartheid so as to reconnect with the era's lost possibilities. Throughout the analysis of Govender's texts, the Group Areas Act emerges as a silent actor that casts its shadow upon his writing. This paper notes how these Acts were detrimental to conviviality and shows how Govender creates textual cartographies that counter the surveilling and controlling of ethnic groups under apartheid. Regarding the Indian presence within South Africa, the paper presents how Govender adapts an Afro-centric position as regards the configuring of this identity.

Keywords

Apartheid, cartographies, chotara, conviviality, hybridity, miscegenation, South African Indian

About the Author

Maurice O'Connor is a full-time lecturer at the University of Cádiz where he read his PhD on Ben Okri. His research interests are currently centred on Indian and Indian diasporic writings. His book entitled *The Writings of Ben Okri: Transcending the Local and the National* was published by Prestige Books, New Delhi, and he has published in journals such as *Wasafiri: International Writing* where his article "The Narcotic Memes of Bombay: Jeet Thayil's *Narcopolis*" appeared in the 2015 autumn edition. He is an active member of the Spanish Association for Interdisciplinary Studies on India and the research group Rathnakara. He has participated in the research and development group entitled "La estética del recuerdo: empatía, identificación, duelo" which explores Indian Ocean writing through the lens of trauma studies. Among his latest publications is "Exploring the Hindu/Muslim Divide through the Partition of Bengal" which appeared in *Revista Canaria de Estudios Ingleses*.

The passing away of Ronnie Govender on April 29, 2021 signaled the death of a living depository of South Africa's recent history. His work thematically spans a period that comprises the era of industrialization (1911–1945), and apartheid/post-apartheid from 1945 onward (Bose 244), although one can say that the indentured labour period (1860–1911) is also elliptically present in his work. The cultural value of Govender's work lies in the fact that his plays and novels afford unique insights into the nature of the Asian position within South Africa. Of underlying importance is how apartheid created a mirror image of the triangulated social configuration that colonial administrations had established in East Africa, with Asians acting as a buffer between the Black/Coloured communities and the white settler community. While his thematic concerns are narrated from the perspective of the Indian community, his work is grounded within an Afro-centric perspective, and this makes Govender's work singular in its representation of the multiple nodes of inter-communal contact that define South African society.¹

LOCATING ASIANS IN SOUTH AFRICA

Apartheid, as well as how it dominated people's lives, is the primary focus of Govender's work. Among Asians in South Africa, this era is also a traumatic event that created an interruption in their life narratives. One particular example of this is the 1946 Asiatic Land Tenure Act which severely limited the amount of land that Asians could buy. This restrictive legislation came hand in hand with an increasing vilification especially of Indians within the white press. A salient example of this vilification can be seen in conjunction with the 1949 anti-Indian Pogrom at Durban. The white press silenced state involvement in the pogrom against Indians while amplifying African grievances against the Indian community. Newspapers disparaged the Indian Passive Resistance campaign and laid the blame solely upon the Asians for the violence meted out upon them by Africans (Lemon 169–74). The 1949 pogrom can be viewed within the context of the Asian body being increasingly under surveillance and the disciplinary gaze of the white hegemony. The curtailing of the natural drive of post-indentured Indians to establish permanent roots in South Africa through the 1946 Asiatic Land Tenure Act represents a fundamental arresting in their aforementioned life narratives. Fiction, in this sense, can be seen as a means to reactivate these truncated life narratives. Furthermore, as shall be discussed later, the novelistic version of *The Lahnee's Pleasure* creates a thematic conduit between the post-indentured past and a post-apartheid era.

There also exists an interesting conceptual link with the systematic violence acted upon the Indian community and the question of postmemory. Marianne Hirsch speaks about how a previous generation's trauma can be transformed into received memory by future generations, something she considers distinct from the actual recall of the witnesses (104–106). In this light, the postmemory of apartheid extends beyond direct familial transfer to embrace a collective imaginary, and the literature of apartheid in general becomes a means to complement and, perhaps, re-configure those collective memories. Certainly, the tropes and images present within Govender's texts interact with the process of postmemory to provide affective triggers that communicate with what Hirsch describes as the "ashes of imagery" (109). This metaphor describes how postmemory approximates memory in its affective force but, contrary to standard memory, is "not actually mediated by recall but by imaginative investment, projection, and creation" (107). These "ashes of imagery" refer to the reactivation and reembodying of cultural memory structures through both individual and familial discourses which Hirsch identifies as being mediated through "aesthetic expression" (111). A specific example of this is Ronnie Govender's grandfather, Veerasamy Govender, an indentured labourer who established himself in the Cato Manor area (Stiebel 119). Further down, we shall discuss how Govender fictionalizes the eviction of Veerasamy Govender from his kitchen garden at Cato Manor and how this became a traumatic memory for the author. The violence exercised by the apartheid regime upon the Asian community as a whole also becomes a form of postmemory, and the interaction between the schemas of cultural transmission and Govender's fictionalization of the Asian presence provides alternative perspectives on South Africa's contemporary history.

To understand the Indian post-indenture context within South Africa, it is useful to keep in mind the third space that the Asian communities of East Africa traditionally occupied. Asians in Africa in general were victims of an imperial practice that created tiered societies of an oppositional nature. For example, the colonial administrations of Kenya, Uganda, Zanzibar, and Tanganyika all created an almost identical three-tier racial system where Indians acted as a social buffer between Africans and Europeans² (Ojwang 118). Within this colonial configuration, Indians effectively became middle men and were denied the opportunity to adopt an organic hybridity where a true sense of Africanness could form a core part of their identity. While Govender in particular has never ceased to celebrate his Indian heritage, he rejects a diasporic classification of his writing and actively promotes a direct filiation with South Africa. It is from this Afro-centric grounding that he negotiates his hybrid identity: an identity that celebrates the singularity of South African Asianness yet denies an imposed colonial configuration of in-betweenness that effectively sought to alienate Asians. In his work we thus find a new negotiation of this hybrid identity located within an Afro-centric location.

Compared to the white European communities in South Africa, indentured and post-indentured Asians have always lived in much closer proximity to Africans. The Joint Declaration of Cooperation signed in 1947 between the ANC, the Natal Indian Congress, and the Transvaal Indian Congress is one example of cross-community solidarity. This close contact, however, has also made Asians more vulnerable to racial conflict, and the specific stigma of the Indian *dukawalla* (shopkeeper/small businessman) who only looks out for himself is something that remains in contemporary times. Karen Flint notes how the lyrics of Mbongeni Ngema's song *Amandiya* singles out the Natal Indian minority as being the cause of Zulu poverty. Ngema's song incited Zulus to rise up and attack the local Asian population who they perceived to be an abusive merchant class (Flint 367).

APARTHEID AND TRUNCATED ETHNIC FLUIDITY

At the Edge and Other Cato Manor Stories (1996), although written during the 1950s, can be considered a "text-site of memory" (Chetty 33) in that it contains affective registers regarding how the Asian community at Cato Manor, Chatsworth, and other townships were historically compromised within the Machiavellian dynamics of segregation. Furthermore, the collection of short stories "resonate with larger claims about South African Indian identities, without simply essentialising or valorising them" (Brown 110). Apartheid, in this respect, was not just about the fraught relationships between the subaltern groups and white supremacy. An important and not so-much explored consequence of the politics of apartheid was the rising tensions between the African and Asian populations. The white settler hegemony had created an official cartography that controlled both the spaces and boundaries of racial identity, and against this state narrative of racial separation and displacement, Govender recreates an "unofficial cartography of knowing, belonging and growing" which becomes a textual performance that "allows the possibility of contesting [these] cartographies" (Brown 109, 111). Through the use of intimately known place names such as "Ahmed's Shop," "Vellema's House," "Adam's Garage," or "Cut-Neck-Bobby's House," Govender contests this official cartography by creating an inner cartography that escapes the surveillance of a nascent apartheid ideology.

One of the most commented-upon pieces in the collection is "1949" which explores the anti-Indian pogrom in Durban on January 13, 1949, where concerted action was taken against Indian traders. The ideological importance of this incident is that it served to bolster a narrative fabricated by white settlers on the incommensurability of racial differences within South Africa. While triggered off

by an Indian stall holder punishing an African boy for stealing, the explosion of violence was informed by deep-standing grievances held by the local Zulus against the Indian trading community.³ With this historical context in mind, “1949” explores the trope of interracial understanding between Black South African and Asian communities and suggests that a white hegemony actively destroyed an already fragile conviviality that existed between them. I use the term “conviviality” through my reading of Steiner who explores “how and under what conditions... people create patterns of human flourishing that privilege mutuality and interconnectedness” (6). Through her reading of Gilroy, Steiner argues for strategies that move societies to go beyond mere tolerance so as to live with otherness where conviviality undoes racism. Gilroy, however, focuses more on Western multicultural societies, and when Steiner speaks of “convivial relation with others in the face of inevitable suffering and asymmetrical power” (10), I infer that she is referencing the asymmetry created by an apartheid regime, an inequality that has continued into the post-apartheid era. With the fragile nature of contemporary South African society in mind, Steiner gives witness to the importance of the concept of conviviality as contesting the current configurations of identity, such as the resurgence of ethnonationalism within post-independence Africa. Conviviality as a social philosophy thus becomes a way to counteract the “prescribing and polarising ways that stress division and difference” (14), and it is a central concern when looking into the complexities generated by the Asian presence in Africa.

From a historiographic perspective, “1949” provides us with an insight into the ways in which the anger of an African underclass was deflected onto Asians, who served as a convenient scapegoat. Percival Osborne, the text’s stand-in for white hegemony, incites his staff to riot, and the text documents how big firms controlled by white capital bussed in *tsotsis* (criminals) into Cato Manor and Riverside to burn the local Indian population. Osborne distributes paraffin to his staff and, speaking in Zulu, tells them that the Indians “deserve what they are getting.” He also incites his staff by saying that the Indians “make a lot of money from [the Zulus]” and “have no respect for [them]” (115). The underlying context of Osborne’s remark has to do with how uMkhumbane (the isiZulu name for Cato Manor) had become home to some 100,000 Zulus who suffered under the exploitive practices of Indian landlords that charged exorbitant rent for appalling living conditions (Steibel 118). This migrant Zulu population, furthermore, had to compete with the already established Asian community composed of petty merchants, municipal service labourers, urban workers, artisanal and sugar refinery labourers, and others. This resulted in Zulus having to accept lower social positions which augmented animosity and further disparaged possibilities of inter-ethnic understandings (Bose 237). Against this thorny social context, Govender, while signalling the abusive practices of Indian landlords, views the pogrom as state-sanctioned. In his memoirs, *In the Manure* (2008), Govender assures that, “No reference is

made to the findings of the official commission of enquiry that a third force had exacerbated the violence among poor people competing for the same resources” (qtd. in Steibel 90). If one takes a cursory glance at the genealogy of apartheid, one finds that racial conflict was initially framed within the perceived threat Indians posed to the white hegemony. Certainly, there existed a “repressive legislation and discrimination pioneered in Natal against Indians [which] was later applied to black South Africans” (Frenkel 12), and this perspective counters received ideas of Asians being opportunistic outsiders. As a textual site of resistance to the silencing and marginalizing of these historical facts, “1949,” through Dumisane (the story’s focal character) activates memories of ethnic fluidity within Cato Manor and reconfigures the idea of animosity between Asians and black South Africans. Dumisane attempts to make his fellow Zulus understand that many Indians were also disenfranchised in relation to the white settler population, yet his allusions to Asian figures such as R. D. Naidu who fought against the color bar are to no avail. Dumisane puts himself between an Asian family and the marauding Zulus, and his death, with a spear embedded in his chest, signals societal fracturing. In light of the strategic pitting of one subaltern ethnic group against another, the narrator assures us that “there was no pity, no reason in the hearts of these malleable souls, held captive by minds more savage in their cunning— the cunning of which empires have been built” (117). These same lines close the 1994 theatre version of the short story which reaffirms Govender’s unchanging position on the white settlers’ strategy of destroying conviviality in order to shore up their power. The play expounds upon those issues brought up in “1949” through an exploration of the social history of Cato Manor where the nefarious effects the Groups Areas Act had on the Asian population are brought to light.⁴

Govender’s fiction attempts to destabilize fixed notions on Indian identity and serves to examine the “evolving historiography of the multicultural and insurgent literary spaces of the edges of empires” (Bose 243–244). “Call of the Muezzin ... To a Slow Samba Beat,” in this respect, inscribes a more optimistic perspective regarding inter-ethnic relationships within the Cato Manor township when compared to “1949.” The narrative focus is weighted towards the trope of ethnic fluidity as a means to re-configure those entrenched attitudes regarding the other. The Asian storekeeper, Shaik, functions as an alternative model for the figure of the exploitive *dukawalla* which, as mentioned earlier, came to dominate a Black collective consciousness within South Africa. The relationship established between Shaik and Elias, an eleven-year-old Zulu, is the narrative vehicle employed to display how affective cross-cultural gestures shape consciousness and remain over time. The trope of musical interculturality is the means by which the text evidences the fluid nature of cultures in contact, and this is performed through Elias’s interpreting of the Kavadi music which is played from the loudspeakers of the Shiva temple. Here, the narrator assures us that, “Ramani Ammal in far-away

India would never have guessed that her songs would one day find resonance on a home-made guitar on the banks of the Umkumbaan River” (“Call of the Muezzin...” 120). These musical crossovers provide a counter-narrative to official white discourses on the incommensurability of racial cohabitation and, despite the burning down of Shaik’s business and the massacre of his children, the text leaves a door open to the ideal of mutual understanding. In a narrative flash forward, Elias now makes a living playing the guitar that Shaik gifted him on the day the 1949 riots commenced. Between sets, Elias plays his hybrid composition based upon the call of the Muezzin at Cato Manor, and this denouement references cross-cultural understanding as a site of resistance against those discourses of division that “1949” denounces through the character of Percival Osborne who insists that, “The races were different and that’s the way it should stay” (20).

The singular aspect of Govender’s work is how he explores miscegenation from the triangulated perspective of white/Asian/Coloured. In his short story “Over My Dead Body,” the author examines the trope of contamination through the character of Gurriah Naidoo who is charged with *crimen injuria*, a legal term in South African jurisprudence which refers to unlawfully, intentionally, and seriously impairing the dignity of another. This trumped-up charge is made in specific relation to a liaison he has with a white prostitute, yet while it is the prostitute who solicits Naidoo, the legal authorities make the prostitute turn state’s evidence so as to incriminate Naidoo through the Kafkian use of *crimen injuria*. Where standard heteronormative discourses would situate the prostitute as the contaminating party, apartheid ideology always deems sexual contact with a black other as inferring a degradation of the white body, albeit it being one on the margins of society. Pujolràs-Noguer, through her reading of Sara Ahmed’s *The Cultural Politics of Emotion* (2004), explores how a European literary tradition treated “blackness as the contaminating element in miscegenation” (4). Here, one finds allusions to filth and disease where, “White women are, by definition, pure, because they do not desire” while “Non-white women, on the contrary, dispossessed of whiteness... are bent to desire and, therefore, polluted and officially undesirable” (9). White South African hegemony displayed a clear anxiety toward miscegenation between White and Asians (among others), and here the aforementioned question of contagion and contamination came into play. However, when one looks at miscegenation between Black Africans/Coloureds and Asians, as we shall discuss further below in conjunction with *Black Chin White Chin*, white anxiety results in the possibility of forging a common front against apartheid. A case in point is the strategy developed by Indian intellectuals in South Africa to identify themselves as “Black,” with the South African Congress promoting interracial political action and a closer identification with the oppressed black majority (Ebr.-Valley 94). This unity, however, was actively thwarted by the apartheid regime, and the active control of miscegenation was one strategy employed.

In his 1974 stage play, *The Lahnee's Pleasure*, Govender uses the mise-èn-scene of an English-style pub, divided into a whites-only section and a Coloured and Asian area, as a means to comment upon the ambivalent nature of cultures in contact. The tone that is used in the play is an ironic one and this is a recurring strategy used throughout the play which both serves to gain the empathy of a heterogenous audience and to destabilise a white supremacist orthodoxy. This is reminiscent of *The Mystic Masseur* (1957) and *Miguel Street* (1959) where V. S. Naipaul employs his brand of postcolonial humour to comment on the ambiguous nature of Asian identity vis-à-vis a local African population and a white colonial one. In comparison to Govender, however, Naipaul's narrator establishes cultural superiority in relation to his characters, with a narrative point of view that persistently speaks from a culturally alienated subjectivity. Govender's narrator, on the contrary, is embedded within an imagined community where the use of local colour and irony becomes a vehicle for the celebration of South African heterogeneity.

Govender, furthermore, examines the conservative nature of South African Asians through a critical view of their constant surveillance of sexual conduct and excessive obsession with racial contamination. The stage play gives voice to this concern through the eloping of the Indian labourer Mothie's 15-year-old daughter and the subsequent dramatic events that this eloping generates. Again, Govender employs a humorous tone that belies these profound questions, and within the play the theme of sexual surveillance is used both as a portrayal of Asian intransigence and of the ambiguous relationship that Asians have with a white settler community. Regarding the latter, the Lahnee (rich, white boss) takes an interest in the case of Mothie's missing daughter, and he uses his contacts within the local police force to locate her. When Mothie's daughter is finally located, a drunken and pathetic Mothie sings and dances for the Lahnee while the barman, Sunny, and the Lahnee clap along (42). This parody brings to light the ambiguous and in-between nature of Asians in a racialised South African society, with the Lahnee's feigned *bonhomie* as a strategy to maintain the white status quo being juxtaposed by Mothie's show of subservience. Compared to the stage play, however, the novel *The Lahnee's Pleasure* (2008) is more celebratory of Asian agency. For example, in a conversation with the barmen, Sunny, Mothie assures him that:

Our girls don't use that (deodorant). You know why? They must bath every day when they light the god lamp. We don't eat beef and pork. We don't smell like the white people. Our girls don't smell like the white girls [...] every day, when I'm on the tractor, my boss's daughters come and play fools with me [...] Me I hold my nose and run away. (21)

Here, Govender reverses the aforementioned trope of contamination through the Hindu codes of purity as a way to contest a white orthodoxy that denies post-indenture labourers such as Mothie their worth.

The 2008 version of *The Lahnee's Pleasure* sets about subverting the status of the Lahnee through the sexual relationship established between the Lahnee's wife, Bronwyn Mary-Anne Braithwaite, and the 18-year-old coloured servant, Fanyana Ngcobo. Through this trope of miscegenation, Govender deconstructs the perceived authority that apartheid held over desired/desiring bodies. One, however, can detect certain simplifications which tend to cancel out those cultural paradoxes presented within the body of the text. The narrated ambiguities and conflicts that naturally resist any simple conclusion are now resolved in a more simplistic manner; a case in point being the novel's ending where we find the Lahnee sleeping in the Salvation Army Relief Hostel while the post-indentured Asians take their symbolic place of power. This overturning of the apartheid power relationship, ultimately, denies the complexities of post-apartheid relationships, and does not examine, for example, the new configurations of power within South Africa and how many Asians still suffer from racialised mindsets inherited from the old regime.

A younger post-apartheid readership would not have the same intimate knowledge that the audience of *The Lahnee's Pleasure* first did when it opened in 1976, and for this reason many historical elements that were elliptically present in the play but had not been specifically voiced come to the fore. Here, it is made much clearer how the figure of the Lahnee was a stand-in for the control and epistemological violence exercised upon South African Indians. One such context is the destruction of the Indian market gardens at Cato Manor during the years of 1958-59, another consequence of the Group Areas Act. The cultural context present here is the transportation of seeds across the *kala pani* (black water or Indian ocean), and their subsequent transplantation in Cato Manor. Transplantation and cross-pollination are cyphers for the cultural transformation of Indians within South Africa, and this same motif of organic hybridity shows how the Asian presence became naturalised in the eyes of Africans and became a means "of claiming an indigenised identity" (Brown 117). In "1949" Elias assures the reader that, on the contrary to the white settler community who considered the Indian vegetation "exotic", for him and his fellow Zulus "the pungent aroma of the curry leaves ... was as natural as daylight" (121) and this created an affective link between the black South African and Indian population. The images of the paw-paw, avocado, and mango, all transplanted Indian seeds that became an African staple, take on metaphoric value as they come to represent both the rhizomatic nature of Asian identity and the naturalisation of this identity upon South African soil. The destruction of the kitchen gardens at Cato Manor thus speaks of a generalised uprooting of Indians from Cato Manor in lieu of the 1950s Group Areas Act, and the dismantling of all multi-ethnic areas reinforces the deliberate strategy on behalf of a white elite to cement its power.⁵

The nascent apartheid regime saw the Indian presence in South Africa as representing a challenge to its authority, and the use of epistemological violence became the antechamber for direct forms of violence, as we saw in the scapegoating of the Asian community in Durban. A public speech of Daniel Francois Malan, South African prime minister from 1948 to 1954, which considered the Indian presence as “an alien element in the population, and that no solution of this question will be acceptable to the country unless it results in a very considerable reduction of the Indian population” gives testimony to the white sense of disturbance regarding the presence of these Asians (qtd. in Chetty 107). The scene at a New Year’s Party in “1949”, for example, dramatizes this when Osborne becomes enraged at the presence of an Asian family described “as fair-skinned as the whites and [...] rich and well-dressed” (116). Osborne’s visceral reaction against the Asian family comes from Osborne’s unconscious insecurity regarding the ordained nature of his white power (116). A useful point of departure to this question is Dyer’s exploration on whiteness which he regards as an invisible asset that is “part and parcel of the sense that whiteness is nothing in particular” (9). Here, Dyer looks at how whiteness both defines normality and fully inhabits it. Similarly, Ahmed assures us that, “bodies are shaped by histories of colonialism, which makes the world ‘white,’ a world that is inherited, or which is already given before the point of an individual’s arrival” (153). Ahmed argues that the constructed quality of being neutral, of going “unnoticed”, means that white bodies don’t have to face their bodies (156). Apartheid ideology was founded on similar understandings of whiteness, where all the other subjugated bodies were measured against its racial image and symbolic power. So, Osborne’s adversity towards the light-skinned Asians is related to his own body; its perceived neutrality and the power it embodies. The presence of the fair-skinned and prosperous Asians could be Osborne’s awakening to his abeyance as regards the perceived natural quality of white supremacy, and this explains his paranoia.

It is also important to look at this question of whiteness from a historiographic perspective. Dyer assures us that during the nineteenth century there was a paradigm shift in the configuration of whiteness which took place in the US as a means to create a separate identity against the Native American and African population (18). This shift entailed a move away from genealogy and towards a biological sense of identity where modern conceptions of “race” were forged (Dyer 18). Dyer, furthermore, argues that the previous model of white genealogy focused upon the Aryans or Caucasians, with the former being posited as “the ancient inhabitants of what is now North West India and Pakistan” (20). Therefore, one could argue that Osborne, on being confronted by this older model of whiteness, is experiencing an uncanny encounter with a modified version of his own whiteness.

ASIAN IN-BETWEENNESS

*Black Chin White Chin: Song of the Atman*⁶ addresses the question of the Asian position vis-à-vis both the African and white settler communities through the narrative of the author's real-life uncle, Chin Govender. Part of the narrative's focus is the in-between nature of the Asian presence in South Africa and how this could be transformed into an organic form of hybridity, grounded within an Afro-centric perspective. The book's title refers to Franz Fanon's text *Black Skin, White Masks* which examines the discursive mechanism of othering, central to the colonial depersonalisation project and which coerced the black subject into an opposition to what was white. Govender, however, deconstructs the white/black binary present in Fanon's work through the trope of miscegenation, with the book's protagonist, Chin, crossing both the black and white colour lines. With reference to the Indian socio-cultural position within East Africa, Stephanie Jones speaks of "the difficulty of escaping a stultifying and brittle past... is often signified... through interracial sexual relationships" (170). This is a significant literary trope in Asian-African writing and is present in the works of Bahadur Tejani, Peter Nazareth, Abdulrazak Gurnah, and M. G. Vassanji alike. Govender appropriates this trope as a narrative strategy to portray his identity positioning that views ethnic realities as not being fixed but, on the contrary, a category constructed in relation to one another. In a settler-dominated society that was increasingly obsessed with racial categories, the body was central to the subaltern predicament, and this is something that Chin, who previously had "never really questioned the separation of the races" (Govender, *Black Chin White Chin* 132) now comes to understand. By viewing subjectivity outside of the cultural lens of the Asian community, Govender thus narrates the historiography of the Indian community in South Africa as being configured through interaction rather than being self-contained. As such, this becomes a discursive strategy that allows Indians to enter into the contemporary history of South Africa. Through the specific use of the trope of miscegenation, Govender gives the Asian body new political significance through his protagonist, Chin, who transforms his relationship with the categories of white and black, thus forging a new nexus of interrelation.

Govender's characterization of Chin is important in the transmitting of this new nexus, and one narrative strategy is the way in which the protagonist negotiates his difference through the reconfiguring of his image. This is performed through the figure of the dandy, and comparisons are made between Chin and Gary Cooper with the former always being impeccably dressed in European clothing. In *Black Skin, White Masks* Fanon appeals to the black subject to reject a mimicry of white cultural practices in order to forge an authentic black culture. Chin, as an Asian who occupies a third space, however, is freed from Fanon's dichotomy of authentic versus fake, and as such the narrative witnesses the formation of a

singular Indian identity that allows his new sense of belonging within South Africa. As a way to understand the political significance of Govender's appropriation of the European dandy, the image of the dandy is seen as being configured through Homi Bhabha's understanding of mimicry. Through Lacan, Bhabha constructs a new understanding of mimicry—something “distinct from what might be called an itself that is behind” (86-99)—and assures us that mimicry behaves like a fetish that mimes forms of authority. In this new configuration, mimicry becomes something inscribed within a particular discourse and appears as “a stain which dislocates and revalues normative knowledges of race, writing, history” (Seshadri-Crooks 378). Seen in this light, Chin's mimicry of whiteness through the figure of the dandy constitutes a strategy that confronts and disrupts the authority of the original, in this case the hegemony of white settler authority within South Africa. When Chin uses his body as an aesthetic vehicle that transcends cultural limitations, both self-imposed and imposed by a conservative Indian community, he is in fact performing what Bhabha defines as the undoing of “the original's mastery” (87).

Within a similar multi-ethnic context, Ceraso and Connelly examine how Indo-Caribbean men's appropriation of the dandy becomes a “feminized version of hegemonic masculinity” (107), while Mohammed argues that Indian-Trinidadian men specifically used miscegenation as a means to garner new positions within a colonial society. The findings from both these studies direct us towards Chin's seduction of his white boss, Greta Schmeling, through the figure of the dandy, as something that lends him new authority within South African society. Here, the political significance of miscegenation is intensified, and Chin's mimicry and miscegenation are destabilizing and subversive in equal measure. The paranoid reaction to his mimicry of whiteness within the novel is dramatized in the scene where Chin Govender and Greta Schmeling walk hand in hand through an area reserved for whites in Port Elizabeth. This generates hostility around the mixed couple and is described as, “an entirely new experience for Chin. He'd never really questioned the separation of the races—he'd had no cause to do so” (Govender 132). The burning of Schmeling's car is symptomatic of the perceived threat to white supremacy given the historical context within which the novel is situated, namely the Immorality Act of 1957.

Against the encroaching of apartheid, *Black Chin White Chin* witnesses the fact that South African society was always much more plural than a white settler hegemony was ready to admit. Chin, on his arrival at the South End district of Port Elizabeth, is astounded to hear, “an elderly Indian woman in a sari ... speaking fluent Afrikaans” (83). Chin's gravitating towards the true meaning of cultural difference gains significance through his close contact with his co-worker and political activist, Michael. In a statement of declarations that underlies Govender's own position, Chin tells Michael that, “my skin [is] the same colour as yours. Don't ever

call me bass” (93). Chin’s subsequent sexual liaison with Michael’s daughter, Grace, is significant in that it marks his movement away from his previous identification with whiteness and towards an Afro-centric position. This shift, however, is marked with ambiguity; while his opening up of the first multiracial hotel, or his strategic support of the fledgling ANC movement all indicate a strong affiliation with a pluralistic sense of African nationhood, his silencing of his relationship with Grace and his refusal to treat it as anything more than casual speaks of the divided nature of his subjectivity. This dissonance is the result of an unconscious resistance informed by a cultural bias that the East and South African Indian community has against miscegenation, particularly where black or coloured Africans are concerned. While Chin’s relationship with Gretta Schmeling was defined by his desire to symbolically occupy the position of white privilege, his liaison with Grace is informed by a sense of Asian superiority, despite his multi-ethnic worldview.

Understanding that heterogeneity posed a threat to its power, some 180,000 people were evicted from ethnically mixed townships, and the series of subsequent Group Areas Act made inter-ethnic relationships in South Africa problematic. This, in part, helps explain Chin’s reticence on establishing a more formal bond with Grace; however, one must look at Chin’s masculinity in conjunction with his inherited sense of Asian exceptionalism as an ingrained cultural bias, and it is here where Govender introduces his criticism of Indian diasporic culture. This sense of exceptionalism strived to eradicate difference, especially from the microcosmic space of the domestic. Crossing the color line, therefore, implies the introducing of an alien element within this sphere, and this can be construed as a violation of the sanctity of the home, constructed upon ethnic essential terms. Asian women in particular were burdened with the preservation of this sense of exceptionalism through the surveillance of sexual conduct within their community, especially where miscegenation was concerned. Diasporic women became the bearers of tradition, coded through ethnicity, whilst the transmission of these cultural mores and the maintaining of cultural cohesion was mediated through patriarchy (Anthias 571-3). The overreaching cult of domesticity defined domestic spaces as “inviolable private domains, to be defended from the strange world outside, which in turn has to be domesticated in order to be rid of its disturbing otherness” (Ojwang 87), and this played a role in isolating the Indian community in South Africa. Jones speaks about how crossing this colour line in East African fiction became a strategy to escape “a stultifying and brittle past” so as to enter a “supple and subtle sense of history” through “interracial sexual relationships” (170). This, we must add, is always viewed from a specific masculine perspective. Jones references David Rubadiri’s *No Bride Price* (1967) as being the first East African novel that specifically addresses racial tensions between Black and Asian East Africans through the trope of miscegenation and, through her in-depth discussion on Rubadiri’s seminal novel, situates gender at the center of questions on belonging (171,173). Hand, through her analysis of

three women's memoirs, namely: Parita Mukta's *Shards of Memory: Woven Lives in Four Generations* (2002); Neera Kapur-Dromson's *From Jhelum to Tana* (2007); and Yasim Alibhai-Brown's *The Settler's Cookbook* (2008), explores gender in conjunction with East African Asian identity, but from a female perspective. Contra Ojwang's reading of the cult of domesticity, Hand assures us that Asian women, "proved themselves more capable of actively welcoming the prohibited and the transgressive and consequently dismantling obsolete barriers" (103). Through her coining of "*clethnicity*", a hybrid term which merges both ethnicity *and* social class as a means of analysis, Hand employs a historiographic approach to her reading of these memoirs so as to discern the distinct ways in which Asian women in East Africa negotiated ethnic identity from disparate social positions (102-107). What emerges from her analysis of these texts is that the East Indian African position, seen from the perspective of gender, was much more heterogenous in nature than previously considered. When setting Hand's research on Asian women's agency against the portrayal of Asian women in *Black Chin White Chin* and Govender's other work, one can observe that the author's perspective is very much drawn from a masculine perspective that silences the aforementioned heterogeneity.

Chin's transformation into a respectable and wealthy man satisfies the bildungsroman narrative arc of the post-indenture Asian gaining respectability against societal odds. There is, however, the question of Chin's denial of his son, Devinthiran (Devs), fruit of his relationship with the coloured woman, Grace. The latter can be construed as a personal failure when set against the revolutionary potential of crossing the colour line. The principal reason the text offers for Chin's denial of his miscegenated son is through how he retreats into himself in the face of an ever-more aggressive apartheid state so as to safeguard the few privileges left to the Asian subject within the apartheid state. As previously stated, the encroachment of a nascent and aggressive apartheid state apparatus informs the mise-en-scène in all Govender's works, and another example of this is the 1942 Restriction of Trading and Occupation of Land Act and the 1946 Asian Land Tenure and Indian Representation legislation, popularly known as the Ghetto Act, which curtailed Indian business ventures and property ownership in white areas (Hand and Pujolràs-Noguer 3, 4). Within this context, Chin is left with little room to manoeuvre and, as such, he retreats into his own community and marries an Indian woman, even though he is not in love with her. This marks a pragmatic shift in his worldview which has turned conservative, yet the memory of his previous enthusiasm for societal change produces in him a state of melancholy.

Unlike Chin, the character of his miscegenated son, Devs, becomes the novel's true focus for change. Devs opposes the apartheid regime by becoming an active member of the Umkhonto we Sizwe wing of the ANC, and alongside Chin's nephew, Guru, represents an alternative model to Chin's ineffectuality. Guru sees his uncle

as a “man of straw, a philanderer who denied his own son, who was ashamed of his own child...” (236). It is in the novel’s final pages where a means of redemption is offered to Chin. On a trip to Robben Island, where Devs is incarcerated due to his participation in the armed struggle against apartheid, Chin’s need for atonement for his shortcomings comes to the fore. The book’s prologue and its final pages thus frame this trope of exoneration and forgiveness, and here Roy sees the narrative structure of *Black Chin White Chin* as pre-empting the restorative narratives of the Truth and Reconciliation Committee (123). Considering that Govender specifically states that from the outset his novel is based upon his family’s history, Roy questions the mode of memory-work employed within the narrative—what she considers to be “a specific kind of piecing together of collective memory”—and considers it to be “ideologically unstable” (124, 132). This instability, Roy insists, is due both to formal inconsistencies, the vacillation of the narrative mode which switches between family saga and bildungsroman literary conventions so as to accommodate Chin’s story, and the fact that Devinthiran’s is, by Govender’s indirect admission, a fictional character. Roy considers the insertion of Devinthiran within the otherwise veridical construction of the author’s indentured and post-indentured genealogy as “betraying its readers” (136). Regarding life-writing as being factually stable is, however, problematic in itself as there is always a strong element of fabrication and coloring of events within the genre, so rather than speaking of betrayal, Devinthiran’s characterization must be viewed as simply serving the author’s personal position regarding hybridity. Therefore, when Devs tells his father Chin that, “Indians need to identify more with the struggle of African people, if they are to secure the future of their children” (132), it is Govender speaking directly to his audience through a literary mouthpiece. The figure of the *chotara* thus becomes a kind of *deus ex machina* that is employed to maintain the utopian spirit present in the novel regarding the crossing of the color line, while Chin’s characterization, on the contrary, is much more faithful to the inherent ambiguities of Asian in-betweenness in Africa.

CONCLUSION

A marked trait of Govender's work is the celebration of the local and this has been part of the author's appeal for a South African audience that enjoys the specificity of his work. Through the use of geographical markers that lay outside the cartographic surveillance of a white settler hegemony, and the employing of South African patois within the dialogues—for example the use of the term *lahnee*—Govender recreated a world that gave witness to the heterogeneity of South African society under apartheid. Particularly, the author relied on an oral-based culture to construct his narratives. Brown suggests that “the moral imperative of the oral folktale” present in his work creates a tendency towards bathos (126). The denouement within *The Lahnee's Pleasure* (2008) is a good example of this. As another trait of the oral folktale, one can also identify a tendency towards over-simplification within his work. The characterization of Devinthiran is an example when one considers how the figure of the *chotara* is a complex one, often running the risk of becoming a cultural fantasy grounded in racism or exoticism. Nonetheless, the image of the *chotara* serves to transmit Govender's belief in cultural heterogeneity and how Asian rhizomatic identity is rooted on South African soil.

When Chetty describes Govender's work as “the vital memory of multiracial living in Cato Manor in a way that contributes to the new national identity” (38), he is referencing a particular ideology prevalent among those anti-apartheid writers who sought to narrate the possibilities of harmonious interracial existence. Govender, as a component of this generation, celebrates his Asian heritage from an Afro-centric position, rather than a diasporic one. Fiction becomes a means to reimagine South Africa's past, and this has an important affective value as, while the exegesis of official historical documentations may provide precise information on traumatic periods, one finds what Tomsy defines as an absence of affect in official documents where a dispassionate/disengaged tone fails to register human emotions (58). Literature, on the contrary, provides the possibility of registering these emotions. Govender's work, in particular, serves to unsettle state narratives on the apartheid period and provides future generations with an affective map of this period.

Notes

1. Taking my cue from Dan Ojwang (2013), I use the term Indian and Asian interchangeably.
2. Compared to East Africa which had three official racial categories, there were four categories in South Africa, namely African, White, Indian and Coloured.
3. Certainly, Africans suffered even more white rule, and the 1913 Native Land Act, which restricted the purchase of land outside of reserves, is one example of African exclusion. “The 1949 Anti-Indian Pogrom and the Crisis in the Natal ANC” provides a detailed insight into the complexities of the Indian position in Durban while outlining the Zulu grievances.
4. In this light, Govender readdresses the “unfairly disproportionate treatment Cato Manor has received in South African history compared to other more famous forced removal places such as Sophiatown (mostly “African”) and District Six (mostly “Coloured”)” (Stiebel 120).
5. Govender’s grandfather had a small kitchen garden in Cato Manor, and the author saw this space as a kind of paradise. Its destruction remained as a traumatic memory all his life (Stiebel 116).
6. The book was first published under the title *Songs of the Atman*. In subsequent publications this title became a subtitle.

Works Cited

- Ahmed, Sara. "A Phenomenology of Whiteness." *Feminist Theory*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2007, pp. 149–68.
- Anthias, Floya. "Evaluating 'Diaspora': Beyond Ethnicity?" *Sociology*, vol. 32, no. 3, 1998, pp. 557–80.
- Bhabha, Homi. *The Location of Culture*. Routledge, 1994.
- Bose, Neilesh. "Performing History and Constructing 'Culture': Ronnie Govender's 1949 and the Romanticism of Historical Memory." *African Studies*, vol. 74, no. 2, 2015, pp. 235–46.
- Brown, Duncan. "Narrative, Memory and Mapping: Ronnie Govender's 'At the Edge' and Other Cato Manor Stories." *Current Writing: Text and Reception in Southern Africa*, vol. 17, no. 1, 2005, pp. 108–28.
- Ceraso, Steph, and Patricia Connolly. "The Destabilization of Masculinity in *A House for Mr. Biswas* and *The Mimic Men*." *Mosaic: A Journal for the Interdisciplinary Study of Literature*, vol. 42, no. 3, 2009, pp. 109–26.
- Chetty, Rajendra. *At the Edge: The Writings of Ronnie Govender*. Peter Lang, 2017.
- Dyer, Richard. *White: Essays on Race and Culture*. Routledge, 2017.
- Ebr-Valley, Rehana. *Kala Pani: Caste and Colour in South Africa*. Kwela, 2001.
- Fanon, Franz. *Black Skin, White Masks*. Translated by Charles Lam Markmann, Pluto Press, 1967.
- Flint, Karen. "Indian-African Encounters: Polyculturalism and African Therapeutics Natal, South Africa, 1886-1950s." *Journal of Southern African Studies*, vol. 32, no. 2, June 2006, pp. 367–85.
- Frenkel, Ronit. *Reconsiderations: South African Indian Fiction and the Making of Race in Postcolonial Culture*. UNISA Press, 2010.
- Gilroy, Paul. *After Empire: Melancholia or Convivial Culture?* Routledge, 2004.
- Govender, Ronnie. "1949." *At the Edge and Other Cato Manor Stories*, Manx, 1996, pp. 107–18.
- . "Call of the Muezzin ... To a Slow Samba Beat." *At the Edge and Other Cato Manor Stories*, Manx, 1996, pp. 119–30.
- . "Over My Dead Body." *At the Edge and Other Cato Manor Stories*. Manx, 1996, pp. 143–56.
- . *Black Chin White Chin: Song of the Atman*. 2006. Harper Collins, 2007.
- . *The Lahnee's Pleasure*. 1976. Ravan Press, 2001.
- . *The Lahnee's Pleasure*. Ravan Press, 2008.
- Hand, Felicity. "Impossible Burdens: East African Asian Women's Memoirs." *Research in African Literatures*, vol. 42, no. 3, Fall 2011, pp. 100–16.
- , and Esther Pujolrás-Noguer. "From Cane Cutters and Traders to Citizens and Writers." *Relations and Networks in South African Indian Writing*, edited by Felicity Hand and Esther Pujolrás-Noguer, Brill Rodopi, 2018, pp. 1–14.
- Hirsch, Marianne. "The Generation of Postmemory." *Poetics Today*, vol. 29, no. 1, 2008, pp. 103–28.

- Jones, Stephanie. "The Politics of Love and History: Asian Women and African Men in East African Literature." *Research in African Literatures*, vol. 42, no. 3, Fall 2011, pp. 166–86.
- Lacan, Jacques. *The Four Fundamental Concepts of Psychoanalysis. The Seminar of Jacques Lacan. Book XI*. Translated by Alan Sheridan, Norton, 1998.
- Lemon, Anthony. *Homes Apart: South Africa's Segregated Cities*. Indiana UP, 1991.
- Mohammed, Patricia. *Gender Negotiations among Indians in Trinidad 1917–1947*. Institute of Social Sciences, 2002.
- Naipaul, V.S. *The Mystic Masseur*. 1957. Vintage, 2002.
- . *Miguel Street*. 1959. Vintage, 2002.
- Ojwang, Dan. *Reading Migration and Culture: The World of East African Indian Literature*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2013.
- Pujolràs-Noguer, Esther. "Desiring/Desired Bodies: Miscegenation and Romance in Abdulrazak Gurnah's *Desertion*." *Critique: Studies in Contemporary Fiction*, vol. 59, no. 2, 2018, pp. 1–13.
- Roy, Modhumita. "What Memory Resists: Indenture, Apartheid, and the 'Memory-Work' in Ronnie Govender's *Black Chin, White Chin*." *Relations and Networks in South African Indian Writing*, edited by Felicity Hand and Esther Pujolràs-Noguer, Brill Rodopi, 2018, pp. 122–35.
- Seshadri-Crooks, Kalpana. "Surviving Theory: A Conversation with Homi K. Bhabha." *The Pre-occupation of Postcolonial*, edited by Fawzia Afzal Kwan and Kalpana Seshadri-Crooks, Duke UP, 2000, pp. 369–80.
- Stiebel, Lindy. "Made in Cato Manor: Ronnie Govender and the Fight to Preserve a Personal/Public Space." *Journal of Literary Studies*, vol. 36, no. 3, 2020, pp. 114–29.
- Steiner, Tina. *Convivial Worlds: Writing Relation from Africa*. Routledge, 2021.
- "The 1949 Anti-Indian Pogrom and the Crisis in the Natal ANC." *KZN HAAS*, <https://phambo.wiser.org.za/files/seminars/Soske2011.pdf>. Accessed 12 July 2022.
- Tomsky, Terri. "Fifty Years On: Melancholic (Re)collections of Women's Voices from the Partition of India." *Trauma Texts*, edited by Gillian Whitlock and Kate Douglas, Routledge, 2009, pp. 61–78.